

Code Switching and Code Mixing Analysis Uttered by Cinta Laura on Helmy Yahya *Bicara* Podcast

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ABSTRACT: The objectives of this final report were to find out the types of code switching and code mixing. This final report focuses in analysis Cinta Laura's utterances in Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast which contained code switching and code mixing in the audio as the data of this final report. Steps taken by the writer in completing this final report was watching a YouTube, downloaded a YouTube video, listen the speech in the video and transcribe the utterance into a script which is required as a data, then the data were analyzed with descriptive qualitative method. The result of this final report found that there are three types of code switching and two types of code mixing. Code switching contained tag-switching which occurred 9 data, intra-sentential switching 44 data, and inter-sentential switching 25 data. Code mixing contained insertion which occurred 80 data and alternation 4 data. The writer expects that this final report can give more information and enlarge knowledge about bilingualism, code switching, and code mixing especially for English Department at State Polytechnic of Sriwijaya.

Keywords: *Code Switching, Code Mixing, Bilingualism*

INTRODUCTION

Rabiah (2018) stated language as a tool used to communicate with other people on a daily basis, as well as a tool for expressing and sharing information or perspectives with others. Therefore, the existence of language enables people to relate and be understood by speakers and speech partners. In order to communicate broadly, people nowadays tend to improve their ability to use and comprehend other languages. The impact of globalization in the current era also makes communication patterns using more than one language a common thing. Individuals or communities who communicate in two languages are referred to as bilingual.

According to Aziz et al. (2019), the majority of people utilize two or more languages on a daily basis, including Indonesians who are typically bilingual. Silaban and Marpaung (2020) stated that, it is common for people in Indonesia to use their first language or native tongue when communicating with their family or community, while English has become widely spoken as

foreign language in the country. When communicating, people who are proficient in more than two languages tend to include words and phrases from other languages into their speech, leading to code switching and code mixing.

Foreign language elements are occasionally incorporated into spoken language through code switching and code mixing. According to Harya (2018), people often mix or switch between languages when communicating with others which can be seen in bilingualism and multilingualism. Bilingualism refers to using two languages, such as Indonesian and Javanese. On the other hand, some people identify as multilingual when they use more than two languages, such as Indonesian, Javanese, and English in their communication. In both bilingualism and multilingualism, language mixing or switching may occur.

Bilingual persons are those who can use more than one language equally (Jendra, 2010). According to Weinreich in Zenab (2016), bilingualism refers to the habit of using two languages bilingually or more alternately. In other terms, bilingualism is the use of two or more languages both individually and collectively. The ability to communicate with others in two languages is known as bilingualism. The world is home to many multilingual people. Because everyone wants to try expanding their knowledge through bilingualism, it happens organically in daily life.

Code switching and code mixing phenomenon become a trend or style of speaking in society. This style also studied in sociolinguistic. This phenomenon affects the programs in some digital media, for example: Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast. Helmy Yahya Bicara is a YouTube channel starring Helmy Yahya that features speakers who have great stories in their lives so that viewers can take a positive message from each episode aired. One of the episodes they made was inviting Cinta Laura as a guest star. Cinta Laura is a female actress of German and Indonesian descent who has long started her career not only in Indonesia but also internationally. In the video, Cinta Laura as a guest star often uses Indonesian and English in communicating for example when

talking about her background, her education, to interpret the meaning of words by mixing or replacing words that are more suitable for use and easier to understand so that code switching and codemixing events have occurred in this video.

In this research, the writer is interested in conducting the research to look for the use of code switching and code mixing. The research about code switching and code mixing, especially on famous Indonesian celebrities who speak at least two languages, has been conducted by several researchers. The first researcher is Khairita and Panobiyasari (2022) with the title "Code Switching by Cinta Laura in Youtube Channel Ngobrol Sore Semaunya". In their research, the result shows that there are 94 data from types of code switching. The second researcher is Gultom (2021) with the title "Code Switching and Code Mixing Used by Boy William Video YouTube Channel". The result after analyzing the video, the writer found 45 data from types of code switching.

Based on the findings of some of those studies, it can be concluded that Cinta Laura has a highest use of code switching compared to other research subjects. This shows that Cinta Laura is compatible with the problems that have been identified and meets the criteria encountered in code switching and code mixing. In addition, Cinta Laura is also an inspirational figure for Indonesian people because she is active in empowering women and protecting children. She always speaks in two languages, Indonesian and English at the same time. The reason she always speaks in two languages is because related to her parents, educational background, and environment. Therefore, the writer chose Cinta Laura as the research subject in this report. This phenomenon then led the writer to further examine code switching and code mixing through a report entitled "Code Switching and Code Mixing Analysis Uttered by Cinta Laura on Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast". This study will analyze the type of code switching and codemixing used by Cinta Laura as a guest star on the podcast.

Code switching served as a means to reflect the speaker's thought process. When a person's language in conveying a message was perceived as ineffective or not understood, they had to switch to a language that the other person could comprehend. Skiba (1997) defines code switching as a communicative exchange between individuals who share specific language codes. This exchange is influenced by various social and linguistic factors that shape how code switching is manifested. In natural conversations between bilinguals, code switching comprises eighty-four percent single-word switches, ten percent phrase switches, and six percent clause switching.

According to Poplack (1980), code switching has three types, namely: (a) tag-switching, (b) intra-sentential code-switching, and (c) inter-sentential code-switching. The first is tag switching. Tag switching is a type of code-switching that falls into the category of free morpheme units found in a sentence or statement in language, particularly in question or assertion. Tag switching that belong to discourse makers are "I mean", "hi", "okay", "you know", "by the way", and others. For example: "It will be okay, ya kan?" The second is inter-sentential switching. Intrasentential occurs within a sentence or clause. It is usually found in the form of a word or phrase. For example: "Perjuangan kamu sudah sangat hebat dan kamu pantas mendapatkan penghargaan tersebut. You made it!" The third is intra-sentential switching. Intersentential switching is considered the most complex form of code switching because it requires the speaker to manage two language systems at the same time", this is the most complex type of code switching because the speaker has to control two language systems simultaneously. Intersentential switching is a type of code switching that requires flexibility for the speaker to be able to speak in two languages at the same time in a more complex form, namely in the form of phrases or sentences. For example: "Tinggal di sini make me bored. Makanan yang dijual mostly not good tapi mau gimana lagi aku harus tetap bertahan until 3 months ahead."

Subyakto (as cited in Rulyandi, 2014), code mixing is the casual use of two or more

languages or language varieties among people we know well. In this informal language situation, it is possible to freely mix codes (languages or language varieties), especially if there are terms that cannot be expressed in other languages. Saddhono (as cited in Rulyandi, 2014), code mixing is the use of two or more languages by incorporating elements of one language into another. In this case, the speaker inserts elements of another language while using a certain language. Nababan (1984), code mixing is a situation in which language changes when people blend two (or more) languages or language varieties in language situations that require the mixture of these languages. Holmes (1992), codemixing can be said to be a rapid code shift that occurs in multilingual societies.

Therefore, it can be concluded that code mixing is a language situation used by speakers by inserting some words, clauses, idioms, greetings, and so on, into a conversation without disrupting the autonomy of the main language being used. Code mixing is commonly used by a speaker in a more casual context, but it is not impossible to do so in formal situations, although it is less likely to occur. If it does occur, it is because there is no appropriate word or expression to replace the language being used.

According to Muysken (2000), code mixing can be divided into three primary categories which are insertion (word or phrase), alternation (clause), and congruent lexicalization (dialect) as describe below. The first is insertion (word or phrase). Regarding the structural properties of certain base or matrix structures, there are alternative approaches that deviate from the traditional concept of introducing new constraints. In this context, the act of code mixing is conceptualized as a form of borrowing, where insertion refers to the integration of lexical items or complete components from one language into the structure of another language. According to Muysken (2000), codemixing is thought of as a procedure that asks for the insertion of an alien lexicon or phrasal category into particular structure. Muysken focuses on noun constructions to illustrate the

concept, but he explicitly acknowledges that the idea of insertion can be expanded to include other types of categorial constructions. This approach, which assumes categorial equivalence and considers functional elements as heads of syntactic constituents, provides an explanation for instances of insertion. For example: “Tentunya politik memiliki stereotype yang berbagai macam.” The second is alternation (clause). Approaches that diverge from the alternation perspective perceive the constraint on language mixing based on the ability or quality of the languages involved at the point of switching. Muysken (2000) said that the phenomenon of alternation is notably common in bilingual communities that have a history of maintaining language separation, but it also occurs in numerous other communities. In contrast to insertion, the bilingual utterance in alternation keeps the two languages distinct as A..B. Thenon-nested A..B..A structure is also seen in alternation, indicating that the elements before and after the “switched string” are not “structurally” connected. Poplack believed that the process of alternating between components from languages A and B is known as alternation code mixing. Language B is unidentified, while language A is dominant. For example: “So this is why I’m so happy actually, karena saya diberi kepercayaan untuk mewakili tempat kelahiran saya.” The third is congruent lexicalization (dialect). According to Muysken (2000), bilingual speakers of closely related languages with roughly equal prestige and no legacy of overt language separation may be particularly associated with congruent lexicalization. These groups may also include second generation migrant groups, dialect/standard and postcreole continua, and these speakers may be bilingual. When two languages share grammatical structures and these structures may be filled lexically with words from both languages, this is referred to as congruent lexicalization. Congruent lexicalization occurs most frequently when dialects and languages with similar structural similarities combine. For example: “Kalian ada yang tau cara convert file dari MP4 ke MP3 ga?”.

Furthermore, research of code switching and code mixing used by Cinta Laura in various digital media has been widely conducted, especially podcasts on YouTube which are currently trending at various ages as they are not only in audio format but also in video format, making it easy to listen and watch simultaneously. The findings of the studies above shows that Cinta Laura often uses codeswitching and code mixing when communicating with her interlocutors in various podcast shows, one of which is Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast where there are many utterances found that contain code switching and code mixing on the podcast.

METHOD

This study utilized a descriptive qualitative research approach to explore a societal problem or issue, specifically focusing on sociolinguistic phenomena such as code switching and code mixing. The data consisting of dialogues of the guest in the Helmy Yahya Bicara podcast were analyzed in the form of utterances. The object of the research was selected from the Helmy Yahya Bicara's Podcast program on January 23, 2023 entitled "Susah Ngasih Judulnya Saking Bagus!" which the writer focuses on speaking of the participants in that podcast especially for Cinta Laura as the guest star. The data was taken from the YouTube official account of Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast.

The source of data is anything that can provide information related to the research. The data used in this report uses two types of data sources. In this report, the writer uses both key informants and supporting informants, as follows key informant is Cinta Laura and supporting informant is Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast. In this report, the source of secondary data is YouTube, which the writer used as a medium to obtain data.

There are several experts who have different opinions about the types of code switching and code mixing. In this research, the research variables are codeswitching and code mixing. The writer used Poplack's (1980) theory to determine the type of code switching and Musyken's (2000) theory to determine the type of code mixing. Here are some indicators to help the writer to ensure

the data is complete and valid:

Table 1 Operational matrix of research variables

Variable	Indicator	Criteria
Code Switching	Tag-switching	a) Inserted a tag in the utterance (short phrase/word)
		b) The tag is in different language
	Intra-sentential switching	a) Only happen within a sentence
		b) Occur within a clause
		c) Occur within sentence boundary
		d) Occur within a word
		e) Occur in the beginning of sentence/middle/end of the sentence
	Inter-sentential switching	a) Occur in a utterance
		b) Speaker completed a sentence, then
c) Switch a different language into next sentences		
Code Mixing	Insertion	a) Occur within a word boundary
		b) Occur when lexical item from one language are incorporated into another
	Alternation	a) Occur when two different languages used in a clause between two languages
		b) Occur within a phrase or a clause
	Congruent lexicalization	a) Occur when two languages have similar grammatical structure

In this study, the observational method was employed for data collection. The observational method involves collecting data by observing the data source, and in this case, it refers to observing language in use as defined by Sudaryanto (2015). Specifically, a non-participatory technique was utilized where in the writer did not actively participate in the dialogues being studied (Sudaryanto, 2015). The researcher did not engage in the dialogues of the videos during the research. In collecting data for this research, there were several steps of collecting the data procedures, such as: 1) Opening the webpage www.youtube.com, 2) Downloading one video on Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast entitled “Susah Ngasih Judulnya Saking Bagus!”, 3) Watching the podcast, 4) Transcribing the utterances of Cinta Laura, 5) Finding all types of code switching and code mixing, 6) Listing types of code switching and code mixing.

After all the required data had been collected through all techniques of data collection, the data were analyzed step by step. According to Bogdan (as cited in Sugiyono, 2010), data analysis refers to the systematic exploration and organization of interview transcripts, field notes, and other gathered materials to enhance one's comprehension of the data and effectively communicate the findings to others. The steps are categorizing the types of code switching, categorizing the types of code mixing, tabulating the code switching and code mixing, and drawing conclusion of the research.

FINDINGS

This study focuses on the types of code switching and code mixing. In this particular section, the writer gathered data from Cinta Laura's utterances in the Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast as a primary source to address two specific issues outlined in the first chapter. The first is finding the types of code switching according to Poplack (1980) theory about three types of code switching: tag-switching, intra-sentential switching, and inter-sentential switching which were found in Cinta Laura's utterances in Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast and the second is finding the types of code mixing according to Muysken (2000) theory about three types of code mixing: insertion, alternation, and congruent lexicalization which were found in Cinta Laura's utterances in Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast.

The Types of Code Switching Used by Cinta Laura

To answer the first statement of problems of study, the writer used Poplack (1980) theory. According to Poplack (1980), there are three types of code switching. In this research of Cinta Laura's utterances in Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast, the researcher found out seventy-eight code switching.

Table 2 Finding and Frequency of Code Switching by Cinta Laura’s Utterances in Helmy
Yahya Bicara Podcast

No.	Types of Code Switching	Frequency
1.	Tag-Switching	9
2.	Intra-sentential Switching	44
3.	Inter-sentential Switching	25
Total		78

Those code switching are appeared through the following types of code switching:

Tag-switching

Tag-switching occurs when a speaker inserts short expressions (tags) from a different language into their utterance. This typically happens at the beginning or end of their speech. In the conversation, Cinta Laura occasionally incorporates language tags into her utterances. In this type of code switching.

Data 057, Ya, hm ya **I mean** kita tadi sudah sempet ngobrol di balik kamera kan (18:20). The utterance above is classified as a tag switching because English tag “I mean” it is showed short express that she clearer something she have just said.

Intra-sentential switching

Intra-sentential switching refers to the occurrence of code switching within a single clause or sentence. This means that the speaker inserts phrases or clauses from another language within the same sentence, resulting in switches happening within a clause or at a sentence boundary. During the Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast, Cinta Laura demonstrated intra-sentential switching by transitioning between different languages within the same sentence. This indicates that code switching took place within clauses or sentences, alternating between one language and another. In this type of code switching.

Data 061, **So you know at that time when I was teenager** kan banyak orangsering nyinyir

tentang aku (19:12). The data counted as intra-sentential switching because Cinta Laura used English first in her sentence and switched into Indonesian within the same sentence in which switches occur within a clause or sentence boundary and relate to another between the languages.

Inter-sentential switching

Inter-sentential switching refers to the phenomenon where a speaker switches from one language to another at the sentence level. This can occur when the speaker completes a sentence in one language and then switches to another language in the subsequent sentence. It can also happen when each clause or sentence is exclusively in one language or the other.

Data 078, **Learning comes in different way**, kadang-kadang juga perlu diketahui oleh masyarakat (23:37). The utterance above is categorized as inter-sentential switching because she has completed a sentence in English “Learning comes in different way” and switched into Indonesian “kadang-kadang juga perlu diketahui oleh masyarakat” in the next sentence. The utterance was classified as inter-sentential switching because it involved switch from one language to another language between sentences.

The Types of Code Mixing Used by Cinta Laura

Based on the second statement of problem study, to answer the second statement of problem of study, according to Muysken (2000) there are three types of code mixing. In this research of Cinta Laura’s utterances in Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast, the writer found out eighty-four code mixing. Those code mixing are appeared through the following type of code mixing:

Table 3 Finding and Frequency of Code Mixing by Cinta Laura's Utterances in Helmy Yahya
Bicara Podcast

No.	Types of Code Mixing	Frequency
1.	Insertion	80
2.	Alternation	4
3.	Congruent Lexicalization	0
Total		84

Those code mixing are appeared through the following types of code mixing:

Insertion

Insertion refers to the act of incorporating lexical items or complete constituents from one language into the grammatical structure of another language. Muysken (2000) described code mixing as a process that involves borrowing and inserting unfamiliar lexical or phrasal elements into an existing structure.

Data 015, Aku menjalani hari-hari aku setiap hari beda karena di dunia **entertainment** kan ga pernah pasti jam-jamnya, ya (05:13). The utterance above is counted as code mixing, because Cinta Laura mixes a word "entertainment" in the utterance in one sentence. This type of code mixing is insertion code mixing.

Data 025, Tentunya tidak mengurangi nilai diri kita atau **self worth** kita (07:17). The utterance above is counted as code mixing because Cinta Laura mixes a phrase "self worth" in one sentence. This type of code mixing is insertion code mixing.

Data 046, Mereka pun berusaha memberikan image bagaikan seorang permaisuri gitu. (13:15) The utterance above is counted as code mixing, because Cinta Laura mixes a word "image" in the utterance in one sentence. This type of code mixing is insertion code mixing.

Alternation

According to Muysken (2000), the process of alternation occurs more frequently in stable bilingual societies with a history of language separation as well occur in many other communities. In contrast to insertion, and keeps the two languages distinct as A...B.

Data 016, Karena hidup yang berkualitas membuat kita memiliki mental yang lebih stabil dan fokus yang lebih kuat untuk menangani setiap pekerjaan yang kita punya, **that's what I believe** (05:33). This utterance considered as alternation code mixing because two languages remain separate in the bilingual utterance. She mixes the two languages English and Indonesian by saying Indonesian first and then continued in English remain separate in the bilingual utterance.

Congruent Lexicalization

According to Muysken (2000), congruent lexicalization is often observed among second-generation migrant groups, dialect/standard and postcreole continua, and bilingual speakers of closely related languages with similar levels of prestige and no established tradition of language separation. However, based on the researcher's observations, congruent lexicalization was not detected in Cinta Laura's utterances in the Helmy Yahya Talk Podcast.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

In this particular research section, the writer explores the outcomes of data analysis and findings mentioned earlier. After analyzed and classified the data based on the types of code switching and code mixing, it is clear that Cinta Laura show the types of code switching and code mixing on Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast.

There are three types of code switching used by Cinta Laura in this study. First, there are 9 data of tag-switching in findings table. For example in the data 057, Cinta Laura said "**You know**, aku rasa orang tuaku beruntung mempunyai anak yang sangat bertanggung jawab". This data is

classified as tag-switching because Cinta Laura said "You know". In her utterance, she wanted to show that the listeners do have the knowledge that she want them to have. Beside of that, specifically tag-switching can be in the form of an exclamation, a tag, or a parenthetical in another language within a sentence which is in different language. In this sentence, the writer analyzed that there is question tag "You know", which gives an understanding.

Second, there are 44 data of intra-sentential switching in findings table. For example in the data 061, Cinta Laura said "**So you know at that time when I was teenager** kan banyak orang sering nyinyir tentang aku". The writer finds the English words "So you know at that time when I was teenager" are uttered by Cinta Laura in the beginning of the sentence. Cinta Laura explained about her youth which was often ridiculed. The data 061 included intra-sentential type of code switching because the words "So you know at that time when I was teenager" as the English words are mixed with Indonesian in sentence boundary or mixing within word boundary. Another example of intra-sentential switching is in data 130 occurred when Cinta Laura said "Hanya karena sebuah paspor gitu **and there's nothing wrong with having two passport**". She wanted to invite audience to know more about the role of a passport itself. This data can be categorized as intra-sentential switching, because intra-sentential switching is concerns language alternation (Indonesian and English) that occurs within a sentence of a clause boundary (Victoria and Robert, 1998). Cinta Laura said "Hanya karena sebuah paspor gitu" after that followed by English utterance "and there's nothing wrong with having two passport". It was happened within a sentence. Therefore, the data above includes intra-sentential switching.

Third, there are 25 data of inter-sentential switching in findings table. In data 115, Cinta Laura says "**I know, you wanna buy house somewhere**, siapa tau 2024 kalau tidak sesuai keinginan kita pindah ke situ". It is categorized as inter-sentential switching because this data shows a switch between two languages, from English to Indonesian between sentences. Cinta

Laura said "I know, you wanna buy house somewhere". That is noun clause, which followed by Indonesian sentence "siapa tau 2024 kalau tidak sesuai keinginan kita pindah ke situ". Therefore, this data included inter-sentential switching because Cinta Laura used English in the first sentence, after that she switched to the Indonesian in the second sentence. Poplack (1980) stated that inter-sentential code switching is the switch involving movement from one language to another language between sentences.

Then, there are two types of code mixing used by Cinta Laura in this study. The first type is insertion. From Cinta Laura utterances on Helmy Yahya BicaraPodcast, the writer found 80 data of insertion in findings table. For example, it can be seen when Cinta Laura inserted phrase "self worth" in data 025. It called insertion since the English lexical class of phrase "self worth" was inserted in her Indonesia's utterance. That utterance included in insertion because insertion of material (lexical item or entire constituents) from one language into a structure of the other language. Another example of insertion is in data 046 occurred when Cinta Laura said "Mereka pun berusaha memberikan **image** bagaikan seorang permaisuri gitu". It can be seen, Cinta Laura inserted word "image" in her Indonesia's utterance. Cinta Laura inserted phrases and words in their utterances. As we can see at findings, the utterances included in insertion because insertion of material (lexical items or entire constituents) from one language into a structure of the other language. The findings were in line with the Muysken theory (2000) approaches that depart from the notion of insertion view the constraints in terms of the structural properties of some base or matrix structure. In addition, a single constituent B (with words b from the same language) is inserted into a structure defined by another language with words from that language.

The second type is alternation. From Cinta Laura utterances in Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast, the writer found 4 data of alternation in findings table. For example, it can be seen when Cinta Laura in data 016 mixed in English "that's what I believe" with Indonesia's utterance to

explain her principles and understanding about quality of life. As we can see from the utterance in data 016, Cinta Laura mixed two languages class of clause in a sentence. In this situation, a constituent from English was followed by a constituent from Indonesia. So, the writer concludes that it includes in alternation where alternation occurred when the speaker mixed clause in the utterance. The findings supported the code mixing theory of Musyken (2000), alternation is the constraint of mixing in terms of compatibility or equivalence of the languages involved at the mix point and clause. In addition, a constituent from language A (with words from the same language) is followed by a constituent from language B (with words from that language).

The third type is congruent lexicalization. As we can see in the findings table, the writer did not find the type of congruent lexicalization. In this case, Cinta Laura is an English native speaker. Native speakers of a language typically prefer to use consistent and fluent expressions in their speech. Congruent lexicalization of code mixing, where elements from multiple languages are combined in a way that follows the grammatical rules of each language, can sometimes result in less fluid or natural communication. Native speakers often prioritize clear communication and linguistic coherence, which is why they tend to avoid this type of code mixing in favor of more seamless language use. This finding was supported by According to Musken (2000), the term congruent lexicalization refers to a situation where two languages share a grammatical structure which can be filled lexically with elements from either language. Therefore, the congruent lexicalization type in Cinta Laura's utterances was not found in this study.

This research has similar findings to the previous research by Langit et al (2022), that found three types of code switching (intra-sentential switching, tag-switching, inter-sentential switching) and two types of code mixing (insertion and alternation), but they used four theories proposed by Poplack (1980) and Muysken (2000), while this research only used two theories proposed by Poplack (1980) and Muysken (2000).

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The writer found the types of code switching and code mixing in this study. Cinta Laura use several types of code switching and code mixing. The result of analysis shows there are 162 data of code switching and code mixing. There are 78 data were code switching and 84 data were code mixing. Cinta Laura frequently used in her utterances from Helmy Yahya Bicara Podcast is code mixing in the form of word which inserts another language (English) into the base language (Indonesian), and the actual phrase inserts another phrase from another language (English) which is different from the base language (Indonesian).

From 78 data of code switching, Cinta Laura used intra-sentential switching the most in her utterances. Inter-sentential switching concerns language alternation that occurs within a sentence or a clause boundary. Sometimes it includes mixing within word boundaries. There are 44 data were intra-sentential switching. Another type is tag-switching there are 9 data and inter-sentential switching 25 data. Then, from 84 data of code mixing, the most frequent type Cinta Laura used is insertion code mixing. Insertion refers to insertion of material from one language into a structure from the other language. Some of the inserted language words are in the forms of single words and some other words are in the forms of phrases. Insertion refers to From the result, there are 80 data of insertion, 4 data of alternation, and congruent lexicalization is zero data. Congruent lexicalization is cannot be found in Cinta Laura utterance.

There are numerous opportunities for further exploration of the topic of code switching and code mixing in the future. The current study focused on analyzing the types utilized based on relevant theories. Hence, the writer recommends that those inserted in this field examine the reasons of code switching and code mixing. Then, the next researcher can use other media platforms such as radio, social media, magazines as potential sources for collecting samples. This will result in diverse variations in future studies on codes witching and code mixing.

REFERENCES

- Aziz, Z. A., Achmad, D., & Fadlun, M. (2019). What types of codes are mixed in Indonesia?: An investigation of code mixing in a magazine. *English Education Journal*, 10(2), 196-211.
- Gultom, R. (2021). Code switching and code mixing used by Boy William video YouTube channel. Thesis. HKBP Nommensen University. <https://repository.uhn.ac.id/handle/123456789/5381>
- Harya, T. D. (2018). Sociolinguistics (code: code-switching and code-mixing). *Lentera: Jurnal Ilmiah Kependidikan*, 11(2), 87-98. <http://jurnal.stkippgribl.ac.id/index.php/lentera>
- Holmes, J. (1992). *An introduction to sociolinguistics*. London: Longman Group UK Limited.
- Jendra, M. I. I. (2010). *Sociolinguistics: The study of societies' languages*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- Khairita, M.N., & Panobiyasari, L. (2022). Code switching by Cinta Laura YouTube channel Ngobrol Sore Semaunya. *The Future of Education Journal*, 1(1), 49-54.
- Langit, A.N.S., Hikmah, I., & Surwanti, D. (2022). Code switching and code mixing on "Ngobrol Sore Semaunya" podcast. *International Journal of English Learning and Applied Linguistics*, 3(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.211111/inelal.v3i1.7410>
- Muysken, P. (2000). *Bilingual speech: A typology of code mixing*. United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press.
- Nababan, P.W.J. (1984). *Sosiolinguistik suatu pengantar*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia.
- Poplack, S. (1980). Sometimes I'll start a sentence in Spanish Y TERMINO EN ESPAÑOL: toward a typology of code-switching. United Kingdom: Routledge.
- Rabiah, S. (2018). Language as a tool for communication and cultural reality disclosure, 10(2), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.31227/osf.io/nw94m>
- Rulyandi, R., Rohmadi, M., & Sulistyono, E.T. (2014). Alih kode dan campur kode dalam pembelajaran Bahasa Indonesia di SMA. *Jurnal Paedagogia*, 17(1), 27-39. <https://doi.org/10.20961/paedagogia.v17i1.36030>
- Silaban, S., & Marpaung, T. I. (2020). An analysis of code-mixing and code-switching used by Indonesia Lawyers Club on TV One. *Journal of English Teaching as a Foreign Language*, 6(3)
- Skiba, R. (1997). Code switching as a countenance of language interference. *Online Internet TESL Journal*, 3(10). <http://www.ecok.edu/dept/english/faculty/lrp/langa2/rlw/discourse.html>

- Sudaryanto. (2015). Metode dan aneka teknik analisis bahasa. Yogyakarta: DutaWacana University.
- Sugiyono. (2010). Metode penelitian pendidikan pendekatan kuantitatif, kualitatif, dan R&D. Bandung: CV Alfabeta.
- Victoria, F., & Robert, R. (1998). An introduction to language. NewYork: Holt, Rinehart, and Winston
- Zenab, A. S. (2016). Kedwibahasaan anak sekolah dasar dan implikasinya terhadap pembelajaran Bahasa Indonesia. Bandung: Siliwangi.